

References

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Biflavones from Leaves of *Cupressus gracilis* and *Cupressus macrocarpa*

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Manuscript received 4 April 1984, revised 12 December 1984,
accepted 15 February 1985

THE genus *Cupressus* Linn¹. (Cupressaceae) consists of about twenty species. Cupressuflavone and amentoflavone seem to be characteristic biflavones to cupressaceae, hence they may serve as a useful taxonomic marker. The present paper deals with the isolation and characterisation of amentoflavone (1), sequoiافلavone (1a) and cupressuflavone (2) from these two species.

1, R=H
1a, R=OH,

2

The dried and crushed leaves of *Cupressus gracilis* (collected from Ooty) were extracted with

boiling acetone. The combined acetone extracts were concentrated under reduced pressure. The dark green gummy mass so obtained was refluxed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), benzene, ethyl acetate and acetone till the solvent in each case was almost colourless. The ethyl acetate and acetone fractions were mixed together and dried under reduced pressure. It was then purified on silica gel column, eluting successively with petroleum ether, benzene, benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1, 1:2), ethyl acetate and acetone. The last three fractions gave usual flavanoid colour test, they were combined and solvent distilled off to give yellowish brown solid. Tlc examination of crude mixture in benzene-pyridine-formic acid (36:9:5) revealed two spots, labelled as CI and CII in order of increasing Rf values. Both the bands were separated by plc (BPF) and eluted by acetone mixed with pyridine (2%).

CI obtained was methylated using dimethyl sulphate and potassium carbonate in dry acetone. The methylated mixture showed the presence of two components (tlc), and were separated by plc. The homogenous components were labelled as CIA and CIB.

CIA, m.p. 173-74°, Rf 0.40, confirmed as I-4', II-4', I-5, II-5, I-7, II-7-hexa-O-methylamentoflavone². The structure of CIB was established as I-4', II-4', I-5, II-5, I-7, II-7-hexa-O-methylcupressuflavone by direct comparison of its methyl ether³ with that of authentic sample².

CII was characterised as I-4', II-4', I-5, II-5, II-7, pentahydroxy-I-7-O-methyl[I-3, II-8]biflavone (sequoiافلavone) by comparison of ¹Hnmr data of its acetate⁴ and methyl ether³ with those of authentic sample.

The dried and crushed leaves of *Cupressus macrocarpa* (procured from Ooty) were also investigated for biflavonyl pigments and led to the isolation and characterisation of the same biflavones, viz. amentoflavone, cupressuflavone and sequoiافلavone. The establishment of structures was made by comparison of physical data and pmr studies of their methyl ethers and acetates with those of authentic samples.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. W. Rahman, Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University for facilities and U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance to one of them (S.K.R.).

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